

PROCI

Peer Review OpenCitations Index: a methodology

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to create a Citation Index following the OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM) that includes typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews a publication (cited entity) [Section 1: Introduction].

Study methodology: The study involves analyzing and manipulating the 2023 Crossref data dump. Crossref is a non-profit organization that facilitates the exchange of scholarly metadata. A software capable of extracting typed entities identified as peer reviews from Crossref dataset and integrating additional information about the reviewed entities from the same dataset is developed. This software generates CSVs and a Turtle file that conform to the OCDM [Section 2: Material and Methods].

Findings: Based on PROCI results, it is determined that the journal receiving the highest number of peer reviews is PeerJ. Furthermore, it is found that only 5,689 out of 348,463 of Crossref’s peer reviews are present in Meta (1.6%), while 70,260 over the 77,660 of the documents in Crossref who received a peer review are stored in OpenCitations Meta (90,5%) [Section 3: Results].

Originality: This study enhances scholarly metadata and deepens the understanding of research impact by proposing a novel citation index that captures peer review interactions.

This study was run strictly following Open Science principles, and, as such, our research outcomes are fully reproducible.

1 Introduction

Peer review is a fundamental stage in scientific communication and publishing as it ensures the validity of published researches. It involves the evaluation of a scholar’s work by independent experts in the same field before it is accepted and published, guaranteeing that the research is rigorous, credible, and free from significant errors or biases. Over time, the peer review process has become fully integrated into the publication process, leading certain journals to become dominant in the scientific world due to their reliability, impacting the journal’s reputation and influence and therefore enhancing venues’ economical value (Baldwin, 2015; Fyfe et al., 2017; Tennant et al., 2017). Despite their

critical role in improving scientific studies, most peer reviews remain unpublished, resulting in a loss of valuable contextual research-related information and obscuring the work of the scientists involved (Tennant, 2018a).

In the last decade, the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)¹ has played a crucial role in proposing systemic changes in how scientific research outputs are evaluated, significantly contributing to the spread of a new approach, Open Peer Review. Open Peer Review refers to models where elements of the peer review process are made accessible to the public, either before or after a study's publication. This approach enhances transparency, fosters trust in the research process, and ensures that the contributions of reviewers are recognized and available to the wider community.

Research indicates that making reviews public can maintain or even improve the quality of feedback, with studies showing increases in the quality of the review and some improvements in constructive feedback and detailed commentary (Rooyen, 2010). Publishing peer reviews enriches research by providing expert insights and highlighting study limitations, thereby enhancing the article's credibility. It also acknowledges the vital role of reviewers by making their contributions part of the permanent scientific record and allowing them to receive credit for their work.

1.1 Crossref and OpenCitations in Open Peer Review

Crossref² is a non-profit organisation that provides digital object identifiers (DOIs) for scholarly content. It acts as a central hub for scholarly communication, enabling researchers to easily locate and cite academic papers, journals, books, datasets, and other scholarly resources. Crossref has been actively involved in facilitating peer review for several years now, extending its infrastructure to manage DOIs for peer reviews. This expansion encompasses a variety of outputs from the peer review process, including referee reports, decision letters, and author responses, across all review rounds. This approach allows for the public availability of peer review history because members can incorporate scholarly discussions not only before but also after publication.

The relationship between a peer review and its corresponding article is constructed within Crossref as a connection between two entities. The citing entity, the review, establishes a relationship with the cited entity through an `is-review-of` link (and `has-review` as reversed property). This relationship is formed between two objects identified with a Crossref DOI. All the metadata of the entities are stored according to a precise data model and are accessible through a REST API system or via the database dump³. Crossref releases a new dump every year, which is valuable for generating quantitative studies on the evolution of the database over time.

1.2 Crossref and OpenCitations in Open Peer Review

The 2023 dump served as the starting point for our research, enabling us to assess which venue contains the most reviewed articles. Considering that journals handle primarily the creation of DOIs for the reviews through Crossref (the alternative being user-side uploads), the most cited journals are the most transparent in the peer review process.

¹<https://sfedora.org/>

²<https://www.crossref.org/>

³<http://dx.doi.org/10.13003/8wx5k>

The second part of our work focuses on the comparison of data coming from Crossref with another non-profit infrastructure organisation: OpenCitations⁴. OpenCitations is an organisation for open scholarship dedicated to the publication of open bibliographic and citation data using Semantic Web (Linked Data) technologies. Open Citations Index treats citations as first-class data entities (Figure 1). The Index does not store metadata about the citing and cited bibliographic entities internally; rather, this information is stored in OpenCitations Meta, which provides bibliographic metadata for all publications involved in the OpenCitations Index.

Figure 1: The diagram of the data model adopted to define the new class `cito:Citation` for describing citations as first-class data entities, which forms part of the OpenCitations Data Model (OCDM). This model uses terms from the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO, <http://purl.org/spar/cito>) for describing the data, and from the Provenance Ontology (PROV-O, <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov>) to define the citation’s provenance.

OpenCitations provides dumps⁵ of its databases as well. Our research led us to study the coverage overlap between OpenCitations Meta and the data present in the Crossref dump. Specifically, we wanted to analyse how many of the entities identified by Crossref as peer reviews are present in OpenCitations Meta and how many of the entities cited as the subject of the review are included in OpenCitations Meta.

OpenCitations Index contains information about the citations themselves. Currently, in OpenCitations, the relationship between peer reviews and cited articles is managed as a reified citation relationship. The way citations are created in OpenCitations is strictly defined through the OpenCitations data model (Figure 2)⁶. According to this model, OpenCitations includes a class of bibliographic entities called “Citation”, which allows the description of citations as first-class data entities. This class has been assigned subclasses (e.g. Author self-citation) and properties (e.g. citation time span) to permit the description of citations in a helpful manner.

Moreover, the data model offers the possibility to link to the Citation entity a subclass of the property `cito:cites` through the property `cito:hasCitationCharacterisation`. In the context of this research, the property to link should be `cito:reviews`⁷. To verify that an entity is a peer review, it is necessary to consult its information on OpenCitations

⁴<https://opencitations.net/>

⁵<https://opencitations.net/download>

⁶<https://opencitations.net/model>

⁷<http://purl.org/spar/cito>

Meta, which indeed distinguishes entities according to their type. At the time of writing, the OpenCitations Index does not have a value that explicitly indicates a peer review relationship.

The central question driving this research is to clarify what modifications should be applied to Crossref data to register the citation relationship in compliance with the OpenCitations data model. This adaptation should address a new requirement: registering this relationship as a “reviewing article” and “reviewed article” relationship.

Figure 2: The diagram of the data model adopted to define the OpenCitations Data Model. This model uses terms from the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO, <http://purl.org/spar/cito>) for describing the data, and from the Provenance Ontology (PROV-O, <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov>) to define the citation’s provenance.

To summarise, our research questions are the following:

1. Is it possible to create a new index of citations which contains typed citations where a peer review (citing entity) reviews (specific citation function) a publication (cited entity)? (RQ1)
2. What is the transformation of the Crossref dump necessary to create such an index to be compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model ? (RQ2)
3. What are the top publication venues in terms of the number of peer reviews received? (RQ3)
4. How many peer reviews in Crossref are included in OpenCitations Meta? (RQ4)

5. How many articles that have been reviewed by a peer review are included in OpenCitations Meta? (RQ5)

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Input data and materials

To answer our research questions, we conducted a study based on two reference databases and their respective documentation. We used the dumps as a source to ensure reproducibility. Specifically, for the Crossref study, we considered:

- The 2023 public data file, which features over 140 million metadata records deposited with Crossref through the end of March 2023. Crossref-generated data and any of their aggregations are published under CC0 licence. Since Crossref metadata is always openly available, the API can be used to keep local copies up to date with new and updated records. All records are included, but metadata completeness and quality vary since it is supplied by Crossref members. Bibliographic metadata is generally required, while other metadata, such as license and funding information, ORCIDs, etc., is optional (though highly encouraged). The records are in JSON format.
- The Crossref data model is crucial for understanding the keys in the JSON files, the most important of which is “type.” This key allowed us to find information about a metadata work type, making it easy to isolate peer reviews.

For the study conducted on OpenCitations, we used:

- The 2024 dump of Open Citation Meta. This dataset contains all the bibliographic metadata (in CSV format) included in OpenCitations Meta. Each line of the CSV file defines a bibliographic resource, totaling 114,621,237 bibliographic entities. The zipped dataset weighs 11 GB and is published under a CC0 licence.
- The OpenCitations Data Model, which is useful for interpreting the keys in the CSV file of the dump, particularly regarding the DOIs of the entities.
- The public repository containing the code used by the organisation to populate the database. It is published on GitHub under the ISC License (ISC). The code was useful in manipulating Crossref data to make it compliant with the OpenCitations data model.

We supplemented the analysis of the data models with further insights by consulting the blogs of both organizations and other official literature. For additional details, please refer to the bibliography. Furthermore, to manipulate the data, we utilized pre-existing libraries, specifically: `pytz`⁸, `polars`⁹, `dateutil`¹⁰, `tqdm`¹¹, `rdflib`¹², `matplotlib`¹³.

⁸<https://pypi.org/project/pytz/>

⁹<https://pypi.org/project/polars/>

¹⁰<https://pypi.org/project/python-dateutil/>

¹¹<https://pypi.org/project/tqdm/2.2.3/>

¹²<https://pypi.org/project/rdflib/>

¹³<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.592536>

2.1.1 The workflow

As we discussed in the introduction, the metadata for each Crossref entity is accessible as a JSON file. The information for the citing entity and the cited entity is stored separately, and the relationship between the two objects is established using the `relation` key, specifically `is-review-of`. In OpenCitations, while the metadata for entities is stored separately in the Meta database, the relationship between citations is encoded and stored in the Index.

To answer our research questions, we analysed the Crossref dump by developing a software with a three-phase workflow:

- Data extraction and processing
- Post-processing
- Data Analysis

Figure 3: The diagram of our workflow. Purple rectangles indicate operations, blue parallelograms indicate data. Input and output datasets are shown in teal parallelograms. The rounded corner boxes identify the RQs to which that part of the workflow answers. The aforementioned described division of the workflow is shown with dotted lines.

2.1.2 Data extraction and processing

This phase takes the Crossref data as input and selects the values from the JSON files that are necessary for alignment with the OpenCitations Data Model. The software developed in this project extracts the information of peer review and non-peer review entities separately to generate distinct CSV files. Only useful information according to the OCDM is extracted. Specifically, for each peer review entity, the DOI, URL, and date of the citing entity are extracted, as well as the DOI of the cited entity. For any non-peer review entity, the DOI, URL, date, title, and ISSN of the publication venue are extracted. The outputs of this operation are then merged based on the cited DOIs to create a single file containing all the data we need. In the Processing phase, data are also combined to create two values required by the OC data model: the OCI and the time span.

The Open Citation Identifier (OCI) is a globally unique persistent identifier (PID) for the identification of open bibliographic citations. Each OCI has a simple structure: the lower-case letters `oci` followed by a colon, followed by two sequences of numerals separated by a dash. Each OCI referring to one of the citations within that database must carry the following pieces of information:

1. A prefix specifying the supplier's database in which the bibliographic citation is recorded.
2. The numerical identifiers used in that database, or the encoded numerical equivalent of (part of) the identifiers used in that database, that uniquely identify the citing and the cited entity.(Peroni & Shotton, 2019)

In our case, the code for identifying Crossref as the source of the record is "020", while to encode the DOIs, we used a relational database provided by OC specifically for this purpose.

The time span is defined as "The temporal characteristic of a citation, namely the interval between the publication date of the cited entity and the publication date of the citing entity. Note that when one or both of the publication dates is given as just 'year', then the citation time span is rounded to the nearest year, and when one or both of the publication dates is given as just 'year and month', then the citation time span is rounded to the nearest month, with the inherent inaccuracies that such rounding involves."¹⁴.

The final step of the data gathering phase involves joining the data of peer reviews and non-peer reviews based on the column containing the cited DOIs. The final output of the process is the creation of three CSV¹⁵ files that separately store:

1. The information about the peer review relationship entity, useful for answering the first and second of our research questions;
2. The provenance data from our software and the Crossref dump, useful for answering the first and second of our research questions;
3. The venues of the cited DOIs, including title and ISSN, to answer the third research question.

2.1.3 Post-processing

Once all the necessary data are extracted, the workflow proceeds with conversion to RDF. To perform this operation, we based our development on the workflow generated for COCI¹⁶ software described in Figure 4(Heibi et al., 2019).

¹⁴<https://w3id.org/oc/ontology>

¹⁵<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11305414>

¹⁶<https://opencitations.net/index/coci>

Figure 4: A flowchart scheme describing the workflow to build COCI.

We can divide this operation into two main steps: the `PeerReview` Class creation, where we initialise a new class object in Python to create a `PeerReview` instance in RDF, compliant with OCDM, and the population of the RDF in which we apply this function to the CSV file resulted from the Processing phase.

In the first step the class `PeerReview` is created. It initialises the properties and classes coming from the CITO ontology¹⁷ and PROVO ontology¹⁸ taking as input the fundamental attributes to create a `cito:Citation` as shown in Figure 1: the subject of this statement will be a URL representing the OCI, as specified in OCDM documentation. For each line of the final CSV file a object `Citation` is initialised and the relative statements are produced. The code’s design allows the possibility of operating on two separate files, one for the provenance and one for the citation creation. Such an implementation allows the system to be applied also on the separated CSV file that we create at the end of our Processing phase.

2.2 Data analysis

2.2.1 Top venue Extraction

To answer to RQ3 it is necessary to extract the information about the venue from Crossref, as specified in Processing phase, collecting the title of the venues and all the ISSN values. The goal of this stage of our workflow is to extract a table with the ISSN values and the venues’ titles along with and their count. The software first considers ISSN values, then titles.

2.2.2 Comparison with Meta

RQ4 and RQ5 require comparing the data extracted from Crossref with those stored in OpenCitations Meta. This operation can be divided in two main steps: DOI extraction

¹⁷<http://purl.org/spar/cito>

¹⁸<http://www.w3.org/ns/prov>

from Meta and DOI Search.

From the CSV containing the dump of OC Meta, the string “doi:” is searched; if found, all characters from the colon to the first blank space are taken. The values found are added to a new CSV file. This output is compared with the final CSV that was the output of the Processing phase. The values are searched between the citing and the cited doi and divided into two files, one for peer review DOIs (cited entity) and one for publications (cited entity).

3 Results

3.1 Main results

3.1.1 Creation of PROCI

The main goal of this research was to assess the possibility of creating an index of peer-review citations (RQ1) in a way that is compliant with the OCDM (RQ2). The results obtained from the workflow explained in the previous sections provide a positive answer to these questions. Citations were created as a first class entities that have as characterisation “reviews”. Starting from the Crossref dump, our research produced 361,117 peer review citations, linking 348,463 peer reviews to 77,660 reviewed bibliographic resources. As shown in Figure 5 (and as expected), there are more peer reviews than reviewed entities, with a ratio of approximately 4.5:1. The RDF resulting from the implementation of our workflow (RQ2) presents 1,357,262 predicates.

Figure 5: Frequency of three Bibliographic entities in PROCI: Citations, Peer reviews and reviewed entities.

3.1.2 Venue analysis

The venues extracted as `container-title` for the reviewed entity are then considered. The top ten venues whose articles received the highest number of reviews are shown in Table 1. As it can be noticed, the top venue is `n/a`, meaning that many articles receiving a peer review are not included in a venue. The top venue therefore is PeerJ¹⁹, an open access peer reviewed scientific mega journal covering research in the biological and medical sciences, with 38,811 reviews received.

Title of the venue	ISSNs	Peer reviews received
n/a	n/a	38811
<i>PeerJ</i>	2167-8359	38597
<i>eLife</i>	2050-084X	30900
<i>Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics</i>	1680-7324	15108
<i>International Journal of Food Science & Technology</i>	0950-5423, 1365-2621	13312
<i>European Journal of Neuroscience</i>	0953-816X, 1460-9568	12032
<i>Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism</i>	1462-8902, 1463-1326	11677
<i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i>	0309-2402, 1365-2648	9443
<i>Brain and Behavior</i>	2162-3279	8273
<i>International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems</i>	2050-7038	7497

Table 1: Top 10 venues per number of peer reviews received.

3.1.3 Comparison with Meta

The final goal of our research was to compare the results of PROCI with entities in OpenCitations Meta (RQ4, RQ5). For what concerns the RQ4 we looked for the peer review stored both in Crossref and Meta. Only a small amount of them was found, 5689 of the total (1.63%). On the other hand, more than 90% of articles reviewed were found (70,260 found in Meta over the 77660 in Crossref) (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Percentage of peer reviews and cited documents in Meta.

¹⁹<https://peerj.com/>

These results show that the PROCI workflow could be a valid supplement to expand the knowledge stored in the current OC data system. While the coverage of articles is significant, the presence of peer reviews is extremely limited.

3.2 Supporting results

In this section, we will present some interesting results that emerged from our research but do not directly address any of our Research Questions. We will structure this section similarly to the previous paragraphs, beginning with the results related to RQ1 and RQ2 (Creation of PROCI), followed by RQ3 (Venue Analysis), and concluding with the results concerning the last two research questions, RQ4 and RQ5 (Comparison with Meta).

3.2.1 Creation of PROCI

The creation of PROCI dataset allows us to calculate further statistics. As mentioned in the previous section, there is a ratio of 4.5 peer reviews for each bibliographical entity. We have calculated the mean to be equal to 4.64. Moreover, in Figure 7 we show the number of articles that received a certain number of peer reviews.

Figure 7: Variation of number of bibliographic entities based on the number of peer reviews received.

We observe that 60% of the articles received less than five reviews, while 7,179 bibliographic entities received ten or more peer reviews (6.8%). As illustrated in the chart above, there must be some entities with an outstanding number of peer reviews. Table 2 reports the frequency of the top ten. The article with more peer reviews of all is *A Review of Prosody, Punctuation, and Dyslexia: Implications for the Use of Speech*

*Technologies*²⁰, a preprint published on Qeios²¹, with 48 reviews.

Finally, using the extracted the time span for the publication of a peer review. Almost 60,000 of PROCI Citations have a negative time span (16.6%). This is significant because it indicates that 16% of peer reviews appear to have been published before the articles they review (Figure 13). This could be considered a paradox—seeing many peer reviews referencing DOIs of articles that are chronologically subsequent. However, we know from Crossref documentation²² that the database includes peer reviews of preprints among its entities. This means that the peer review was conducted on a preprint, and once the preprint became a final publication, its final DOI was associated (using the property ”is related to”) with the peer review entity. This makes sense, as the publication itself benefited from that peer review to improve.

entity reviewed	Peer Reviews received
10.32388/6wopal.2	48
10.32388/xmjxce	44
10.5194/se-2015-134	40
10.32388/odcenj	38
10.1002/vms3.1119	37
10.32388/7lebd5	36
10.32388/66uhui	35
10.32388/xchu6m	34
10.1002/vms3.475	34
10.32388/elvm4l	33

Table 2: DOI of the 10 reviewed entities with the most peer reviews received

²⁰<https://doi.org/10.32388/6WOPAL.2>

²¹<https://www.qeios.com/>

²²<https://www.crossref.org/blog/discovering-relationships-between-preprints-and-journal-articles/>(last accessed on December 12, 2024.)

Figure 8: Percentage of Citations with negative timespan.

3.2.2 Venue analysis

Regarding the venues, we also analyzed the top ten venues for negative time spans (Figure 14), revealing interesting results. Notably, the highest value is from *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*²³ with 12,329 cases, ranking third in the number of peer reviews received. This aligns with the interpretations discussed in the previous paragraph: for 20 years, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* has been a pioneer in transparent peer review. Submitted preprints, reviews, and author replies are published and permanently archived on the journal’s website²⁴.

Another observation we made regarding our venues concerns the number of those without an ISSN. Over 38,811 articles are published in anonymous venues (no ISSN or title), while the top ten venues without an ISSN, as reported in Crossref, are shown in Figure 10.

²³<https://www.atmospheric-chemistry-and-physics.net/>

²⁴https://www.atmospheric-chemistry-and-physics.net/peer_review/interactive_review_process.html(last accessed on December 12, 2024.)

Figure 9: Top ten venues with highest number of negative time spans.

Figure 10: Ten most cited venues were no ISSN was extracted from Crossref.

3.2.3 Meta Comparison

Out of 361,117 Citations, 337,244 of them link to an Entity stored in Meta (93% of the total). On the other hand, only 5,428 of these entities in Meta have their peer review in it, with a ratio of 1.02:1. Figure 11 and Figure 12 show the loss of bibliographic entities in Meta: the first one shows the number of cited publications that have their peer reviews in Meta, The second plot shows the number of peer reviews in Meta having their cited publications in Meta.

Figure 11: Number of reviewed entities in Meta and number of those whose peer review is also in Meta.

Figure 12: Peer reviews in Meta having also their cited publications in Meta.

3.2.4 Anonymous vs. Non-Anonymous Peer Reviews

In the world of scientific publishing, the topic of anonymity in peer reviews has always been a significant topic. Two different perspectives have been in contrast: the proponents of blind reviewing (single or double (Snodgrass, 2007) believe that maintaining the

anonymity of the reviewer allows them greater freedom. On the other hand, within the Open Science community, the paradigm of Open Peer Review (Ross-Hellauer, 2017b) has gained traction, which includes among its core principles the removal of anonymity for both the author and the reviewer. For this reason, a supporting result of our work is the analysis of the authors.

A) Number of anonymous peer reviews

The first aspect we focus on is the distribution of peer reviews extracted by Crossref that are anonymous or not. Therefore the number of Peer Reviews that have at least one author was computed. The result shown in Table3 represent the expected situation in which the percentage of peer review signed is way lower than the anonymous ones Figure13.

Author	Count
Known	102223
Anonymous	246240

Table 3: Count of known and anonymous authors

Figure 13: Percentage of Citations anonymys or not in PROCI.

B) Top venues per anonymus peer review received

Next, we considered which venues had the highest number of anonymous peer reviews. The plot in Figure14 shows these results in absolute value and as a percentage of the total peer reviews received. It emerges that eLife has the highest number of non-anonymous peer reviews, suggesting a possible adherence to the principles of Open Peer Review. On the other hand, PeerJ shows a very low relative number of those, the lowest of all.

Figure 14: Top ten venues with highest number of non-anonymous peer reviews received and their percentage distribution.

C) Number of authors per peer review

Finally, we take in this section the number of authors per peer review. In Figure 15, we analyzed the number of authors who co-wrote a peer review. As someone could expect, almost one out of five of the signed are authored by one person only (81,012). while around 15402 peer review as less than ten authors (16% circa).

Figure 15: Percentage of Peer reviews per number of authors.

Since the idea of a peer review being written by more than ten people is intriguing, we decided to examine the distribution of these values. Thus, in Figure 16, we plotted the number of authors for each document of interest against its frequency. As the plot shows, 86.6% of these documents have fewer than 15 authors (4252). It appears that there are fourteen peer review that have 100 or more authors which appears an extremely high value.

We tried to reason it checking them online but not significant data was found. We leave here their DOIs for further explorations 4.

Figure 16: Distribution of peer reviews having 10 authors or more.

Peer review DOI	number of authors
10.1111/irv.13039/v2/response1	1652
10.7554/elife.60060.sa2	1382
10.1111/dom.14857/v2/response1	473
10.7554/elife.60675.sa2	159
10.7554/elife.59391.sa2	158
10.7554/elife.67569.sa2	149
10.7554/elife.66877.sa2	147
10.7554/elife.58728.sa2	137
10.7554/elife.66537.sa2	136
10.1002/2688-8319.12032/v2/response1	118
10.1111/ecog.06125/v3/response1	118
10.1111/ecog.06125/v2/response1	118
10.7554/elife.57443.sa2	108
10.7554/elife.67113.sa2	100

Table 4: Peer reviews with 100 authros or more (descending order)

4 Discussion and Conclusions

The PROCI workflow described in this article appears to be a valid approach for extracting peer reviews from Crossref and organizing them in a manner compliant with the OCDM. Each citation is assigned an OCI and subsequently linked to all data related to its creation and provenance, including the citing entity, cited entity, creation date, timespan, and provenance data.

The methodology proposed here builds on the COCI workflow (Heibi et al., 2019), adapting it to the purpose of this research. It should be noted that the ingestion workflow in OpenCitations has changed significantly since then (Giambattista, 2023) (Figure 17). This model first creates the bibliographic entity in OC Meta (assigning an OMID) and then creates the relation as OMID to OMID. The first step was not a requirement for this project; therefore, it will be possible to expand it further in future developments to follow the same workflow. Additionally, we observed that approximately 16% of peer reviews show a negative time span, which could be due to linking the publication process (from reviewed pre-print to published article) in those journal that allow pre-print publication.

This workflow led to the creation of software used to generate the first PROCI Dataset based on Crossref.

We also investigated the venues with the highest number of peer reviews received. A total of 38,811 peer reviews point to articles without a specified venue, which might indicate articles published online outside the traditional publishing system, though this is not certain. The most reviewed venue is PeerJ, with 38,597 peer reviews.

Finally, we compared the data generated in our research with OC Meta. The results indicate that while more than 90% of reviewed entities in Crossref are also stored in Meta, only 1.6% of their peer reviews are included. It is believed that the creation of PROCI might lead to an increase in Meta coverage, aligning with the renewed interest of the Open Science community in Open Peer Reviews.

The study highlights key trends in peer review anonymity and authorship. Most peer reviews remain anonymous. Certain venues, such as *eLife*, exhibit adherence to Open Peer Review principles, while others, like *PeerJ*, show minimal signed reviews. Authorship patterns reveal that single authorship is predominant, with 16% of reviews involving fewer than ten authors. These findings underscore the dominance of anonymity in peer review and hint at gradual shifts toward transparency in line with Open Science practices.

Figure 17: Latest published ingestion workflow for OpenCitations.

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